

TREATMENT OF CUTANEOUS BASAL CELL CARCINOMA WITH PDL LASER AND ITS COMBINATION

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Abstract. Skin basalioma (SB) is the most common type among malignant skin tumors. Metastasis of basal cell skin cancer is rare. However, the recurrence rate of the disease is high. Basal cell carcinoma occurs in areas of aesthetic importance such as the forehead, nose, temples, and other regions. Therefore, when treating SB, it is necessary to pay attention to the aesthetic aspect as well. A study of 37 patients with basal cell carcinoma of the skin was conducted in the outpatient department of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Center of Dermatovenereology and Cosmetology from 2022 to 2024. The patients underwent histological, dermatoscopic, and high-frequency ultrasound examinations. Treatment was administered taking into account the clinical type of skin basal cell carcinoma, the depth of the lesion, and the degree of proliferation. The study included 37 patients: 2 with superficial basalioma, 32 with nodular basalioma, 2 with ulcerative basalioma, and 1 with pigmented basalioma. Based on the results of high-frequency ultrasound (HFUS) diagnostics and its correlation with morphological parameters of proliferation intensity, criteria for selecting treatment methods were developed: PDL laser for superficial forms with a depth of less than 2000 μm ; PDL laser combined with imiquimod for other forms when the depth exceeds 2000 μm . If the depth of basal cell carcinoma is less than 2000 μm , using a PDL laser as monotherapy is considered the most optimal method.

Keywords: skin basalioma, PDL laser, HFUS-skin examination.

Introduction

Among all malignant neoplasms in humans, basal cell carcinoma ranks third in frequency after stomach and lung cancer. Its prevalence among skin tumor lesions, according to various researchers, ranges from 50 to 90%, accounting for more than 75% of all types of skin cancer (Seidl-Philipp). Basal cell carcinoma is characterized by intense angiogenesis (Minars, Belova LA). Many countries, including Russia, lack an oncological registry for basal cell carcinoma of the skin (BCC), resulting in inaccurate epidemiological data. Trigger factors for BCC development include excessive exposure to ultraviolet radiation, ionizing radiation, and chemical carcinogens. The risk group comprises individuals with fair skin (Fitzpatrick phototypes I, II, III), males, those with a family history of the disease and immunosuppression, and people over 60 years of age (Pisklakova). Solmetova studied 1215 patients with basal cell skin cancer during the period 2015-2019, and found that the basal cell tumor incidence in Uzbekistan is 9.7 per 100,000 population (Solmetova, 2022).

Morphologically, BCC originates from the basal layer of the epidermis and its appendages, has low metastatic potential, but is locally invasive. Treatment of BCC includes a wide range of

methods, from the local use of medicinal products in the form of creams to surgical treatment, as well as various methods of destruction, laser therapy, chemotherapy, radiation therapy. Local-distributed and metastasizing forms are treated with radiation and systemic therapy, hedgehog signaling inhibitors vismodegib and sonidegib are used in systemic treatment of basalomas, PD1 inhibitor semiplimab is the second line of therapy. For local treatment, several groups of drugs are used:

a DNA synthesis inhibitor (5-fluorouracil);

an immunomodulator from the imidazoquinolinamines group - an activator and agonist of TLR-7 and 8, which triggers an adaptive immune response with subsequent activation of the Th-1 response and production of cytokines TNF-alpha, IL-12, IFN-gamma (imiquimod);

NSAIDs, particularly diclofenac, which inhibits COX-1 and COX-2 involved in tumorigenesis; a keratinocyte necrosis inducer and inflammatory response activator (ingenol mebutate);

retinoids, including 3rd generation ones (tazarotene and adapalene), which selectively bind to beta and gamma nuclear retinoic acid receptors (RARs). The use of imiquimod, NSAIDs, and ingenol mebutate for skin cancer treatment is approved by the FDA, while the use of retinoids is considered "off-label" (Micali, Nanda, Stanley).

A large randomized multicenter study involving 12 centers in the United Kingdom, which examined and treated 501 patients, compared the effect of imiquimod to surgical treatment. The study showed that their effectiveness after 3 years of observation was 84% for imiquimod and 98% for surgical treatment, respectively, with no significant difference in the cosmetic outcome between these treatment methods. However, side effects such as itching occurred in 83% vs 52% of cases, and weeping in 63% vs 32.8% of cases when using imiquimod and surgical treatment, respectively (Fiona Bath-Hextall).

A meta-analysis of 13 studies involving 4,256 patients demonstrated that Imiquimod increases the rate of histological clearance in basal cell carcinoma and significantly increases the frequency of complete response. However, it does not affect the success rate or tumor-free survival probability compared to other treatments. Furthermore, patients receiving Imiquimod experienced adverse events more frequently than those receiving other forms of treatment (Hong-Xia Jia 1, Yan-Ling He).

It was established that the effectiveness of photodynamic therapy exceeding 95% was observed with basal cell carcinoma spread depth up to 0.7 mm, and 100% cure rate with 5% imiquimod cream was achieved in cases with tumor thickness ≤ 0.4 mm [McKay K.M. et al., 2013; Bichakjian C.K. et al., 2016]. Surgical excision is preferable for tumors with a thickness greater than 2 mm [Bichakjian C.K. et al., 2016]. As evident from the above, the choice of treatment method for basal cell carcinomas depends on the characteristics of BCC. Dermatoscopy allows for a preliminary diagnosis, while verification is carried out by histological examination. It is important to clarify the degree of progression risk (high/low), which determines the treatment strategy. For low risk of progression, Mohs surgery is used, while for metastatic forms, systemic therapy with Hedgehog signaling pathway inhibitors is employed (Naik).

Ki-67 is a marker of cell proliferation and is expressed to varying degrees in all phases of cell activation, namely G1, S, G2, and M. From the initial phase of cell activation G1 to the M phase, this marker increases and reaches its maximum during the metaphase of mitosis. In the initial phase of G1, the Ki-67 marker is located in the centromere of satellite DNA and in the telomere of the chromosome. In the middle phases of cell activation, the Ki-67 marker appears in

the nucleolus, and by the G2 phase, it is expressed both in the nucleolus and in the karyoplasm. When the cell transitions to postmitotic G₀, the Ki-67 marker is degraded by proteosomes, undergoes complete catabolism, and is not expressed in interphase cells.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

We examined 37 patients who underwent inpatient treatment at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Center of Dermatovenerology and Cosmetology between 2022 and 2024. The average age of the patients was 61.6 ± 1.65 years, with 14 men (38.2%) and 23 women (61.8%), and a male-to-female ratio of 0.61. When studying the duration of the disease, it was found that in most patients (28 cases, 75%), the first lesions appeared more than 6 months before seeking medical attention; the average duration of the disease was 10.1 ± 2.4 months, and all patients were seeking treatment for this condition for the first time.

Study Population

The study included 37 patients, During dermatoscopy, the following types of basal cell carcinomas were identified: superficial, nodular, ulcerative, pigmented, and scleroderma-like; however, scleroderma-like basal cell carcinoma was not observed in our patients (Figure 1).

Independent and Dependent Variables

In our study, a proportional relationship was identified between the results of high-frequency ultrasound examination of the skin and immunohistological examination for 4 different clinical forms of cutaneous basaliomas. Additionally, a correlation was found with dermographic features: the patient's age, sex, and Doppler imaging results.

Data Collection Methods

For ultrasound scanning, a specialized high-resolution digital ultrasound system "DUB skin scanner" (manufactured by "TPM GmbH," Germany) was used. It was equipped with ultrasound probes with frequencies of 75 and 33 MHz for skin ultrasound scanning and 18 MHz for Doppler examination of tumor blood flow. Based on the Ki-67 marker, it is possible to calculate the cell proliferation index. Using the modern software QuPath-0.5.0-ImageJ platform, it is possible to count expressed cells without human intervention with 98.5% accuracy at 200x and 400x magnification using a special command.

Statistical Data Analysis

The depth of clinical forms of cutaneous basaliomas was studied in comparison with superficial basaliomas. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant for all analyses.

Results

Four different clinical forms of cutaneous basal cell carcinoma were included in our study. We diagnosed them using high-frequency ultrasonography. The epidermal surface was finely bumpy in ulcerative forms and predominantly coarsely bumpy in nodular forms. The epidermal unevenness index was highest in nodular forms, while in pigmented and ulcerative forms, it was 2-2.5 times lower than in nodular forms, but 20 times higher than in superficial forms. This indicator can be used to differentiate the clinical form of basal cell carcinoma in complex cases. When assessing the depth of basal cell carcinoma invasion, we found that nodular forms had the highest value of this indicator, while in terms of width, all types of basal cell carcinomas did not differ from each other statistically significantly (p>0.05) (Table 1).

High-frequency ultrasonography signs of basal cell carcinomas depending on the clinical form (Table 1).

Characteristic	superficial	nodular	ulcerativa	pigmented
width within the tumor body, μm	7300 \pm 1989	10980 \pm 470	11110 \pm 877	9909 \pm 1456
tumor thickness (depth of invasion), μm	1031 \pm 630	5510 \pm 300*	3780 \pm 489*	3902 \pm 699*
spread of the lesion to epidermis layers, %	100	100	100	100
spread of the lesion to dermis layers, %	0	100	100	83
Pattern (presence of hypo-heteroechoic inclusions), % of cases	33	10,5*	56*	17
Pattern (presence of hypo-anechoic inclusions), % of cases	17	60,5*	44,5*	83
Pattern (presence of punctate hyperechoic inclusions along the periphery), % of cases	66	100*	100*	100*
irregular edges of the lesion, %	0	60,5*	67,5*	68,0*
presence of inflammatory infiltrates, %	0	21*	100*	34*

*- statistically significant at p<0.05 compared to the superficial form

The high positive expression of the Ki-67 marker exceeding 20% indicates that the mitosis process in atypical cells of the basal area continues in the G2 phase. In clinical forms of basalioma, the expression level of the Ki-67 marker ranged from 62% to 10%. A correlation was established between the Ki-67 expression level and the depth of cutaneous basalioma, with a reliability level of 92.85% (Figure 2).

The relationship between basalioma depth and ki67 expression 92,85% (Fig.2)

37 patients underwent PDL laser and PDL+imiquimod treatments. During ultrasound examination of the skin, if the depth of the skin basalioma was $\leq 2000 \mu\text{m}$, only laser therapy was applied; for depths $\geq 2000 \mu\text{m}$, complex therapy was administered, i.e., laser therapy combined with a local immunomodulatory cream. Positive results were obtained in 26/37 cases. Patients were monitored for 6 months, and no recurrence of the disease was observed. 11/37 of our patients remain under clinical observation.

Outcome of nodular basalioma treatment (2-tab.)

Duration of combination therapy	Results of the HIFU-skin examination		
Before treatment		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Epidermis thickness: minimum value $117 \mu\text{m}$; maximum value $250 \mu\text{m}$; 2. The acoustic density of the epidermis has decreased to 168 units; 3. Characteristic of the inner contour of the epidermis facing the dermis: coarsely bumpy; 4. Thickness of the tumor $6200 \mu\text{m}$; 5. The acoustic density of the dermis has decreased to 3 units; 	
After 10 days		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Epidermis thickness: minimum value $107 \mu\text{m}$; maximum value $130 \mu\text{m}$; 2. The acoustic density of the epidermis has decreased to 30 units; 3. Characteristic of the inner contour of the epidermis facing the dermis: coarsely bumpy; 4. Thickness of the tumor $6200 \mu\text{m}$; 5. The acoustic density of the dermis has decreased to 3 units; 	

After a month		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Epidermis thickness: minimum value 117 μm; maximum value 230 μm; 2. The acoustic density of the epidermis has decreased to 138 units; 3. Characteristic of the inner contour of the epidermis facing the dermis: coarsely bumpy; 4. Thickness of the tumor 4355 μm. 5. The acoustic density of the dermis has decreased to 12 units; 	
After 3 months		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Epidermis thickness: minimum value 117 μm; maximum value 170 μm; 2. The acoustic density of the epidermis has decreased to 138 units; 3. Characteristic of the inner contour of the epidermis facing the dermis: coarsely bumpy; 4. Thickness of the tumor 2100 μm. 5. The acoustic density of the dermis has decreased to 42 units; 	
After treatm ent		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Epidermis thickness: minimum value 90 μm; maximum value 105 μm; 2. The acoustic density of the epidermis has decreased to 150 units; 3. Characteristic of the inner contour of the epidermis facing the dermis: coarsely bumpy; 4. Dermis thickness: minimum value 1346 μm; maximum value 1640 μm. 5. The acoustic density of the dermis has decreased to 65 units; 	

Discussion

Considering the pronounced vascularization of basal cell carcinomas according to Doppler ultrasonography data, the use of selective vascular-specific laser destruction using laser radiation with a wavelength of 585-595 nm is justified. This treatment method is based on the concept of selective photothermolysis [7]. Limitation of thermal damage within the target lesion is achieved if the laser wavelength with selective absorption and sufficient energy is delivered with a pulse duration shorter than the time required for the target to cool down. A pulsed dye laser (PDL laser) generates laser radiation with a wavelength of 585-595 nm, which is well absorbed by oxyhemoglobin in blood vessels, partially transforming it into methemoglobin, and is limited in depth of penetration to the papillary layer of the dermis. There are several studies dedicated to investigating the use of laser radiation with a wavelength of 585-595 nm for the treatment of

various forms of basal cell skin cancer. The treatment effectiveness ranges from 71 to 92% complete regression of basal cell skin cancer foci after 4 procedures performed every 2 weeks.

Imiquimod was prescribed to activate macrophages, as the drug's mechanism of action involves activating Toll-like receptor 7 and enhancing the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines - IFN-alpha, TNF-alpha, IL-12, which leads to the initiation of a Th1-type immune response and cytotoxicity. It is necessary to ensure the removal/destruction of tumor cells, as basal cell carcinomas exhibit an extremely wide variety of somatic mutations, far more than in other types of malignant tumors. Most of these mutations show signs of UV-induced damage: substitution of cytosine with thymidine, C>T or CC>TT, and heterozygosity for the PTCH1 gene, or mutations in the TP53 gene located on chromosome 17q13. Depending on the effectiveness of the therapy, 1 to 3 procedures were performed at 3-week intervals. The following parameters were used: energy density in a 595 nm pulse - 10 J/cm²; pulse duration - 3 ms. The criteria for the effectiveness of the selected parameters were the appearance of purpura, darkening, or the emergence of a grayish tint in the treated area. The treatment area includes at least 5 mm of visible healthy tissue surrounding the tumor.

Conclusion. In our study, the complex treatment of skin basalioma with PDL laser and imiquimod showed positive results in 70% of cases, while the remaining 30% of patients are still under observation. Prior to treatment, our patients underwent dermatoscopic examination, high-frequency ultrasound of the skin, and histological studies. After confirming the diagnosis, treatment was prescribed based on the clinical type and depth. According to the high-frequency ultrasound results, the average depth of superficial basalioma was 1031±630 μm, nodular basalioma 5510±300 μm, ulcerative basalioma 3780±489 μm, and pigmented basalioma 3902±699 μm. Based on these findings, we used monotherapy for cutaneous basaliomas up to 2000 μm in depth, and complex treatment for those deeper than 2000 μm. The PDL laser used in our study had an energy density of 10 J/cm² at a wavelength of 595 nm; the effectiveness of the 3 ms pulse duration was evaluated by the following parameters: appearance of purpura, darkening, and graying of the laser-affected area. Each patient was assessed on the 10th day of treatment, at 1 month, and at 3 months (Tables 2,3). In conclusion, PDL laser treatment and its combination therapy prove to be safe, effective, and non-invasive methods, and we recommend them as alternative treatment options for skin basaliomas.

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